

POLITICAL SCIENCES

THE COVERAGE OF AZERBAIJAN-CHINA RELATIONS BY THE AZERBAIJANI MEDIA IN THE ERA OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract

The article introduces the monumental achievements of Azerbaijan-China relations from the establishment of diplomatic ties till the present day, emphasizing the unprecedented role of Azerbaijani media outlets in developing and strengthening Azerbaijan and China bilateral relations in the modern world. The article also discusses the special importance of the role of mass communication of the People's Republic of China (PRC) in the development of bilateral relations between countries in the era of modern information technologies. The purpose of this article is to examine the current dynamics of Azerbaijan-China relations by analyzing the media coverage of Azerbaijan news providers. This article employs quantitative and qualitative research of historical notes, documents, and reports of the Azerbaijani press regarding Azerbaijan-China relations. Based on the analysis, the author comes to the conclusion that the relations between the two countries have deepened and broadened smoothly over the last decade, even reaching a new phase of bilateral partnership - the level of the strategic partnership with the impact of One Belt One Road Initiative of China via modern technologies.

Keywords: Azerbaijan-China Relations, Azerbaijani Journalism, Modern Technologies, One Belt One Road Initiative of China.

Introduction

In the age of modern technologies, journalism serves as a critical mechanism for documenting the latest and most significant social and historical developments. It plays a unique role in shaping public opinion and provides firsthand accounts that become primary sources for historians. Similarly, international relations also utilize media outlets to shape narratives, disseminate information, and engage with global audiences, etc. Apparently, the link between international relations and journalism is deeply intertwined. Therefore, it is believed that the study of the relations between Azerbaijan and China by means of media coverage analysis has certain novelty and foresight.

In history, the Azerbaijani press medium has basically gone through four stages coinciding with the political movement: 1) Newspapers and magazines published under tsarist Russian rule (1832-1917); 2) printed organs published during the Azerbaijani Democratic Republic (1918-1920); 3) printed publications of the Soviet era (1920-1991); 4) publications printed since the restoration of independence (after the collapse of Soviet Union in 1991 to the present). [8]

With the fall of Soviet Union and the establishment of the Republic of Azerbaijan, fourth phase of Azerbaijan press becomes booming, today, there are more than 40 types of publishing newspapers and periodicals, 9 national TV stations (of which a public service broadcaster and 3 more state-run channels), over 12 regional TV stations, 25 radio channels in Azerbaijan. The online media such as APA, Day, Trend, Turan, Azeri-Press, News Azerbaijan and Interfax are all independent media outlets operating actively in Azerbaijan. The official news agency of the Republic of Azerbaijan is AZERTAC, which was founded in March 1, 1920 by the government of Azerbaijan Democratic Republic.

Although it had different names during the years of Soviet power, AZERTAC still continuously disseminates exact and operative information on political, and economic issues, science, education, culture, health, sports, environment in several language including Azerbaijani, Russian, English, French, German as well as Arabic since its establishment. There is little doubt that AZERTAC plays a pivotal position in reporting and strengthening Azerbaijan-China relations.

In the meantime, the Chinese media landscape is a complex and dynamic system composed of state-owned enterprises, private companies, traditional media, and new media. Major news outlets include Xinhua News Agency, China Daily, People's Daily, CCTV (China Central Television), and massive regional newspapers and channels. However, the advancement of the internet and mobile technology has transformed the media landscape in China. During a professional report held by Chinese media groups in 2020 [12], only about 7 percent of people obtain news information via traditional media, namely newspaper and TV channels. Around 77.25% of people get news information from WeChat notifications, 39.02% from Douyin (the Chinese version of TikTok), 24.61% from Toutiao (news headlines), and 24.03% from Weibo (social media website). Generally speaking, China's media industry can be classified into several categories based on public preference. For instance, traditional media like print media and television; digital media (online news portals and social media, such as Sina News, NetEase, Tencent News, WeChat, and Weibo); broadcast media including radio and podcasts; publication by academic journals and Think Tank; as well as the most popular new media apps like Douyin, Kuaishou, and Little red note, etc.

The new media landscape in China has also gone through a significant transformation since 2016, marked by the rapid evolution of various platforms that

seamlessly blend information dissemination with e-commerce capabilities. Platforms like Douyin, Kuaishou, and Little red note have emerged not only as social networking sites but also as vibrant marketplaces where users can purchase products directly through engaging content. A key aspect of this dynamic environment is the participation of influential figures, such as singers, actors, writers, and other celebrities, who leverage their popularity to create diverse content formats, including short videos, live streaming, podcasts, and articles. This approach not only enriches the user experience but also appeals to a wide range of audiences, fostering deeper engagement.

For instance, the Embassy of the Republic of Azerbaijan to the People's Republic of China and AZERTAC have launched their WeChat public account, which largely enhance communication and engagement Azerbaijan and Chinese public. It can serve as a platform for sharing news, cultural events, and important information about bilateral relations. Ultimately, these developments illustrate how new media in contemporary China serves as a powerful tool for engagement, enabling users to connect with content and commerce in unprecedented ways.

As far as one may concerned, the impact of journalism can be examined domestically and globally. On a national level, a news report informs citizens about local issues, government policies, and community events, fostering an engaged and informed electorate. It can also reflect societal values, norms, and debates, shaping public discourse and influencing cultural identity. Meanwhile, owing to globalization, media becomes more interconnected, and events in one part of the world can have immediate implications elsewhere, creating a more complex web of international relations. How the media frames international issues can significantly impact perceptions. For example, the portrayal of conflicts or diplomatic efforts can shape narratives that either promote peace or escalate tensions. As a result, it is essential for both Azerbaijan and China to leverage media effectively to enhance their diplomatic and international standing. Thus, examining media coverage of Azerbaijan-China relations will chiefly reveal how journalism shapes narratives around diplomatic ties and global partnerships.

Reviewing Azerbaijan's Perspective on Azerbaijan-China Relations (2014-2024)

From the ancient "Silk Road" to today's great restoration of "Silk Road", history chronicles the comprehensive and sustainable bilateral relations between Azerbaijan and China. The modern era of relations between Azerbaijan and China began on December 27, 1991, when the People's Republic of China recognized Azerbaijan's independence, and on April 2, 1992, the two countries established diplomatic relations. In 1992, China opened an embassy in Baku, and in 1993, Azerbaijan opened an embassy in Beijing. It is apparent that there are countless historical events worth commemorating since the establishment of diplomatic relations between the two countries. Scholars currently studying the relations between Azerbaijan and China can consult massive database, including but not limited to historical

books, newspapers, manuscripts, and even cultural works, handicrafts, as well as witnesses who experienced these historical events.

The records from Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Azerbaijan indicates that frequent high-level visits occurred between two sides during thirty years. [7] The President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Ilham Aliyev, paid visits four times to China, on March 17-19, 2005, August 8, 2008, May 20-21, 2014, December 8-11, 2015, April 24-27, 2019 respectively. A myriad of humanitarian cooperation, economic cooperation, and cultural events had been conducted on mutual agreements by two countries. Since 2013, the initiative of Belt and Road project has provided huge opportunity for Azerbaijan and China to further enhance bilateral ties. Apart from the areas mentioned above, foreseeable collaborations also will be implemented in the fields of energy, agriculture, and hi-tech to diversify Azerbaijan's economic system. In March 2024, Hikmat Hajiyev, the Assistant of President of Azerbaijan for Foreign Policy Affairs, was designated to visit to China for discussions and consultations with Chinese counterparts on how two countries can further advance cooperation. He noted that digital transformation is the number one priority for Azerbaijan in national priorities, based on its sustainable development goals. Some Western media outlets like to hype up in relation to Chinese companies, Hajiyev stressed that this is unfair treatment of China. He said that he has been using Huawei products for many years and the country looks to expand cooperation with more Chinese companies including with Huawei. [5]

It is noticeable that the Republic of Azerbaijan attaches special importance to bilateral relations with the People's Republic of China and is interested in deepening and broadening these relations in all areas. Azerbaijani President Ilham Aliyev stated with CGTN reporter that he met Chinese President Xi Jinping many times, they had very productive discussion about two countries' future cooperation. [6] Over the course of thirty years, innumerable cooperation and collaborations demonstrate that Azerbaijan and China are good partners and trustful friends. Initially, two countries have established quiet solid political platforms supporting the territorial integrity and sovereignty. And cooperate with two nations on numbers of economic projects based on close political ties. In order to diversify petroleum-dominated economy in Azerbaijan, Baku is willing to work with Belt and Road Initiative of China. Currently, Azerbaijan has completed necessary segments of transportation infrastructure in middle corridor of BRI, including Baku-Tbilis-Kars railway, the International Free Economic Zone at Alyat, and Azerbaijan as a newly established tourist transport center. [4] As an active participating of BRI project, favorable foreign policies and commercial environment have been created to foreign investment, particularly the Chinese companies.

In July 2024, Azerbaijan and China declared jointly to form a strategic partnership, during the Summit of Shanghai Cooperation Organization in Astana, it is definitely a highlight moment in the history of China-Azerbaijan diplomatic relations. In accordance with

this declaration, for a period of one year (20 July 2024 to 20 July 2025), the valid ordinary passport holders of the People's Republic of China who plan to visit the Republic of Azerbaijan are not need a visa for entry. [9] And this declaration marks the development of Azerbaijan and China relations has entered a new strategic partnership level. Bunyad Huseynov, the ambassador Extraordinary and plenipotentiary of the Republic of Azerbaijan to the People's Republic of China wrote an article to CGTN China on the occasion of the 75th anniversary of the establishment of the People's Republic of China, he pointed out that two countries are reliable partners for each other in all spheres of cooperation, and support each other in key issues related to the national interests of two nations. But the most important thing is that all these activities are aimed at sparking an interest among two friendly peoples, worthy of prosperity and limitless opportunities. [3]

Education is crucial for personal and societal development. In a narrow sense, it empowers individuals with knowledge and skills, promotes critical thinking, and fosters informed citizenship. Nevertheless, from a broad view, education also plays a key role in economic growth, helping to reduce poverty and inequality. The educational programs were carried out between Baku and Beijing as early as 1990s. The author of the first Azerbaijani-Chinese Dictionary, Rashad Karimov, mentioned in an interview that in 1995, through an agreement between the Azerbaijani Ministry of Education and China, he came to Beijing Language and Culture University to study Chinese as the only student among six students in the Chinese Language Department of Baku State University in Azerbaijan to receive a Chinese government-funded scholarship. [11] Annually, about 30-50 students are being selected by the Ministry of Education of two countries, as exchange students, to complete their bachelor, master, even PhD academic studies (in Azerbaijan so called HTP scholarship). As a matter of fact, education exchange programs enhance many benefits by facilitating cross-cultural understanding and collaboration. Participants gain exposure to different educational systems, languages, and perspectives, enriching their learning experiences. These HTP scholarship programs can also strengthen Azerbaijan-China relations, and create networks that support innovation and problem-solving across borders.

Correspondingly, the two Chinese language and culture institutions, the Confucius Institutes, at Baku State University (2011) and Azerbaijan University of Languages (2016) contributed great effort in promoting traditional Chinese language and culture. Along with Azerbaijan's higher education institutions, and museums, they presented the most authentic Chinese values and cultural events. Taking the Azerbaijan National Carpet Museum hosted the event "Dragon Welcomes Spring, Chinese New Year Festival" as an example, it was organized by the Azerbaijan National Carpet Museum and the Confucius Institute at Azerbaijan University of Languages with the support of the Embassy of the People's Republic of China in Azerbaijan. [2] The festival lasted five days covering traditional Chinese

tea ceremony, calligraphy (painting cards with hieroglyphs), Kung Fu, paper cutting and other Chinese culture related master classes, and offering chances for audiences in Baku to feel the atmosphere of the Chinese New Year. Plenty of Azerbaijani media reported and documented this event, such as AZERTAC, CBC TV, Report.az, Xalqazeti.az, and the Ministry of Culture official channel.

The culture and tourism industry of Azerbaijan has been proliferating in recent years. The number of Chinese tourists who visited Azerbaijan during the first eight months of 2024 was a record-breaking 26,866, more than double the figure from the same period in 2023. [1] The peak tourist season occurs in the spring and winter. Chinese visitors love Azerbaijan's history, culture, nature, hospitality, food, and unique blend of modern appearance and ancient soul. The visa-free policy and the availability of direct flights between Baku and Beijing by Azerbaijan Airlines (AZAL) are significant factors that encourage Chinese individuals to visit Azerbaijan. The events were organized by the Azerbaijan Tourism Board (ATB) in partnership with Azerbaijan Airlines (AZAL) on September 24th to further strengthen the tourism relationship between Azerbaijan and China. These measures are a big step forward in Azerbaijan's efforts to strengthen its ties with the Chinese tourist industry.

In summary, the bilateral relations between the Republic of Azerbaijan and the People's Republic of China have had an in-depth development during the past decade. The friendly relations between the two countries are based on political mutual trust, economic cooperation, cultural exchanges, and people-to-people connectivity. Both the Azerbaijani people and officials are optimistic about relations with China. The media coverage in Azerbaijan is a mirror of the development of relations between Azerbaijan and China, reflecting the productive interactions between the two countries.

Methodology

This study adopts a mixed-methods approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative research methods, to comprehensively analyze the quantity, content, and format of news reports related to China and China-Azerbaijan relations published by various Azerbaijani news websites, channels, and news agencies from 2014 to 2024. The selected media sources include AZERTAC, Trend News Agency, APA, AzTV, Real TV, CBC TV, İTV, IRS, AzerNews, oxu.az, vuzglyad.az, Report.az, and others. These platforms were chosen due to their prominence and wide readership in Azerbaijan, ensuring a representative sample of the media landscape. The combination of quantitative and qualitative methods allows for a detailed understanding of both the volume and nature of media coverage, offering valuable insights into the role of media in shaping public perceptions and bilateral relations.

Data Analysis and Results

The study covers a ten-year period from 2014 to 2024, capturing a comprehensive view of media coverage over an extended time frame. The author hopes to identify Azerbaijan's attention on China by assessing

the high-frequency words, content trends, and the amount of reports on China in Azerbaijani news reports, and propose feasible recommendations based on the issues reflected in this analysis.

Types	Name	Ownership	Recurrence	Language
News Agency	AZERTAC	State-run	Daily	AZ/EN/RU/DE/ES/AR/CH/FR
	TURAN	Private	Daily	AZ/EN/RU
	TREND	Private	Daily	AZ/EN/RU/TR/FA
	APA	Private	Daily	AZ/EN/RU/AR/FR
Television	AZTV	State-run	Daily	Azerbaijani
	REALTV	Private	Daily	Azerbaijani
	CBC	State-funded	Daily	Russian
	ITV	State-funded	Daily	Azerbaijani
Press / Online	AzerNews	Private	Weekly	English
	oxu.az	Private	Daily	AZ/RU/TR
News Provider	vzglyad.az	Private	Daily	AZ/EN/RU/DE/ES
	Report.az	Private	Daily	AZ/RU/EN

Figure 1. overview of selected Azerbaijani Media Outlets

Initially, Azerbaijan State News Agency (AZERTAC), was the foremost official and predominant news agency in Azerbaijan. The AZERTAC has an extensive communications network throughout the country and abroad, with branches in 21 countries. News is available in eight languages: Azerbaijani, English, Russian, French, German, Arabic, Chinese, and Spanish. Today, AZERTAC has maintained a 20-year steady partnership with China's leading news agency, Xinhua News Agency. Moreover, China Daily, the Chinese top-tier English-language newspaper, signed a cooperation agreement in 2019. The Chairman of the Board of AZERTAC, Vugar Aliyev,

hailed AZERTAC's tight cooperation with Chinese media groups, as well as their mutual support for each other's initiatives. And Chinese news websites have included dozens of AZERTAC news articles, emphasizing Azerbaijan's successes under President Ilham Aliyev's leadership.

According to the quantitative research method, the author finds out that AZERTAC has contributed 19526 search records to introduce China, the contents touch upon political, economic, cultural, educational, technological, and other aspects Since 2014. Summarizing all news reports in terms of nine keyword search records on AZERTAC's online website, azertag.az, a bar chart and analysis have been completed below:

Figure 2. Indicators of Data analysis of Keyword Search Records on azertag.az

The bar chart illustrates the most frequently referred keyword regarding China by AZERTAC reportage from 2014 to 2024. Beijing, China's capital, ranks first in terms of news coverage, having been cited 6694 times. The second most reported word, Shanghai, is

1622 times as its status is one of the major international centers for finance, business, and economics. Besides these two key locations of China often occurring in Azerbaijan news stories, city names such as Guangzhou, Xi'an, Urumqi, Wuhan, Chengdu, and Tianjin

also occupy an enormous number of the data since Azerbaijani businessmen have frequent trade contact in these cities. In other words, these Chinese cities have already developed into the crucial transportation hubs connecting China and Azerbaijan. Since 2013, the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) has become the top priority between Azerbaijan and China [10]; therefore, BRI, about 1221 times, is the third most common keyword that appears in reports. In addition, Chinese companies can also be considered a hot word in Azerbaijan, citing 1007 times; there are 18 permanent enterprises in Baku, the oldest of which has been operating in Azerbaijan for 20 years. At this point, Huawei, the resident office of the Chinese information and telecommunications giant company in Baku, is undoubtedly one of the most used keywords on AZERTAC's online website. Moreover, the keywords like Chinese culture, language, and Confucius Institute are also high-frequency words. Chinese has already become one of the most popular and worth learning languages in Azerbaijan due to its high demands and high returns. Understanding Chinese culture and values is another essential tip for dealing with customers from China. Surprisingly, according to a report by the Chinese Ministry of Commerce in Azerbaijan, the local mainstream media in Azerbaijan has a positive attitude toward China. Except for certain impassioned comments in news stories, there have been a few unfavorable reports denouncing the Chinese and Chinese firms in Azerbaijan. Indeed, media literacy could be one of the explanations for this occurrence.

Secondly, Azerbaijani Press Agency (APA) and Trend News Agency, the news providers highlighting the analytical reports and feature articles on the information of political, economic, energy developments, and financial aspects both domestically and globally, also have built a close relationship with the Chinese Embassy in Azerbaijan considering the amount of coverage of Azerbaijan-China political, economic, social, and technological activities. In addition to the general feature of other online news sites concerning the current events in China, it is noteworthy that trend.az has addressed the great importance of Azerbaijan-China bilateral relations in supporting medical aid during the outbreak of the novel corona virus. For instance, a report on April 2, 2020, written that Deputy Minister of Foreign Affairs Ramiz Hasanov appreciated that the Chinese test kits for detection of COVID-19 infection, provided to Azerbaijan, are an indicator of this friendship. He warmly thanked the Chinese people and the government for their huge support during the pandemic. By the same token, there is a great deal of reportage on their website demonstrating that China and Azerbaijan have strong bonds and strategic cooperative counterparts in the age of modern technologies.

Thirdly, a group of Azerbaijani national television channels, such as AzTV, Real TV, CBC TV, and İTV, are still important sources of information for citizens in Azerbaijan. Unlike black-and-white paragraphs and columns in newspapers, television news is much more colorful and time-saving. The TV programs from the four channels mentioned above often broadcast authentic China-related reports. On April 2, 2024, after thirty-

two years since China recognized Azerbaijan's independence, AzTV's "SÖZÜMÜZ İMZAMIZDIR" filmed a special program dedicated to Azerbaijan and China relations. Two AzTV journalists reported from Baku and Beijing on the two nations' huge achievements in politics, economics, trade, culture, and tourism in the last 32 years. The show attached great importance to BRI projects and the role of the Confucius Institute in Baku. Furthermore, İTV has paid special attention to teaching the Azerbaijani language at Beijing Foreign Studies University in China as well as Azerbaijani students who learn Chinese in Baku. This innovative and interesting interview was planned by the "Sabahın Xeyir Azərbaycan" TV show in which two Chinese students from Khazar University and an Azerbaijani student from middle school shared their language experiences. All the Azerbaijani TV shows gradually unveil the mystery of China to the audience in a friendly and approachable way. At the same time, they introduced the audience to the questions they were interested in, such as why Chinese people want to learn Azerbaijani. Is Chinese difficult? What is the impression of Azerbaijan in Chinese?

At last, in addition to the mainstream media outlets, some alternative news providers also featured a fair amount of information about China. According to the language preferences of news readers, they can choose, for instance, AzerNews in English, oxu.az and Report.az in Azerbaijani, vzglyad.az in Russian, etc. With attention to the rapid development of Azerbaijan-China relations, the media tend to build good contact with the Chinese embassy in Baku so that they may swiftly get actual and effective information regarding China's current releases. On June 17, 2024, Charge d'Affaires Ding Tao from the embassy of the People's Republic of China in Azerbaijan published a signed article titled "The One-China Principle Cannot Be Challenged" on vzglyad.az. This article introduces through fair and objective historical facts that Taiwan has been an inseparable part of China since ancient times and expresses to the Azerbaijani people the Chinese people's determination to firmly defend the territorial integrity of China.

Conclusion

Generally speaking, the Belt and Road Initiative largely enhanced Azerbaijan-China relations. Since 2014, the two countries' relations have advanced to a new phase. In terms of politics and diplomacy, high-level visits and interactions between the two countries are highly common, and many mutually beneficial policies have been jointly proposed; Economically, the two nations are collaborating to revitalize the Silk Road, fully capitalizing on Azerbaijan's strategic location at the crossroads of Asia and Europe, and transforming Baku into a transportation hub connecting Asia and Europe. At the same time, the two countries share a common understanding of people, and business trade and tourism thrive. So far, in terms of education and culture, the two countries' exchange scholarship program has enabled hundreds of students to fulfill their goals of studying abroad while also building a bridge of friendship between the two countries. Furthermore,

collaboration between the two countries in technology and renewable energy is gradually advancing. It is believed that the COP29 summit in Baku brought together Azerbaijan and China to employ technology and renewable energy to protect the world on which we rely for survival. Ultimately, media coverage can reflect the trajectory of relations between the two countries to a large extent. Understanding and comprehending the characteristics of journalism, as well as making effective use of media to report, are critical subjects for all countries.

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